

Common Pitfalls in Bioimage Analysis Pipelines and How to Avoid Them

BioVoxxel – Scientific Image Processing & Analysis

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Target audience: Graduate programs, core facilities, research groups and institutions

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Summary

Bioimage analysis pipelines are a central component of modern biological research. At the same time, they are prone to structural, methodological, and organizational errors that can lead to **non-reproducible results, biased measurements, or avoidable loss of time.**

This whitepaper describes **typical pitfalls** that are regularly observed in academic research environments and outlines **concrete measures** to prevent them. The focus is not on individual software tools, but on **pipeline design, data integrity, and institutional frameworks.**

Context: What Is a Bioimage Analysis Pipeline?

A bioimage analysis pipeline refers to the **sequence of processing steps** by which raw image data are transformed into quantifiable results, typically consisting of:

1. Data acquisition
2. Pre-processing (e.g. noise reduction, normalization,...)
3. Segmentation (e.g. extraction of objects or areas of interest)
4. Measurement / feature extraction
5. Statistical analysis, interpretation & visualization

Errors introduced at early stages often propagate throughout the entire pipeline and frequently remain unnoticed until results become difficult to interpret or reproduce.

Pitfall 1: Unclear Separation Between Image Editing and Image Analysis

Problem

In many workflows, **visual optimization** (e.g. contrast adjustment) and **quantitative analysis** are not clearly separated. If images optimized for presentation are subsequently used for measurements resulting data are mostly flawed.

Typical consequences

- systematic measurement bias or error
- non-traceable or incorrect intensity values
- violations of good scientific practice in publication figures

How to avoid it

- strict separation between:
 - analysis images (raw or minimally processed data)
 - presentation images (including editing acceptable for scientific figures)
- documentation of all processing steps and parameters
- training users to understand the methodological difference between *visual enhancement* and *quantitative processing*

Pitfall 2: Lack of Standardization in Pre-processing Steps

Problem

Pre-processing steps (e.g. background correction, filtering) are often:

- manually adjusted (biased)
- chosen differently by different users (subjective)
- insufficiently documented
- impact on data integrity is not properly understood

Typical consequences

- results depend on the individual user and contain personal bias
- lack of comparability between experiments
- analyses are not re-traceable nor reproducible
- data alteration propagates and accumulates without being noticed

How to avoid it

- definition of standardized pre-processing steps per data type
- consistent application of processing steps on all data supposed to be compared
- use of documented macros or scripts
- solid training in sound parameter selection instead of “trial and error”
- sound understanding of the impact on data of individual processing steps

Pitfall 3: Overfitting of Segmentation Parameters

Problem

Segmentation algorithms are frequently **optimized for single example images** or **homogeneous training data** without testing robustness across entire and/or heterogeneous datasets.

Typical consequences

- good performance on training images
- poor performance on real datasets (overfitting and bad generalization)
- systematic bias (e.g. toward specific object sizes or pixel intensities)

How to avoid it

- train, test and validate segmentation on representative image series
- use objective quality criteria whenever possible
- document the decision logic behind parameter choices
- automate image analysis for robust testing and reproducible application
- include quality controls at different levels during the pipeline

Pitfall 4: Missing Validation of Measurement Results

Problem

Measured values are often processed further without checking whether they are **biologically plausible** or methodologically valid.

Typical consequences

- statistically sound but biologically insignificant, meaningless or confounded
- loss of confidence in analysis results
- non-reproducible results get published and propagate in literature

How to avoid it

- plausibility checks and quality control (e.g. size, intensity, count ranges)
- alternative analytical procedures to corroborate findings independently
- visual inspection of selected measured objects (quality control)
- combination of automated analysis and spot checks

Pitfall 5: Lack of Reproducibility Due to Manual Steps

Problem

Many pipelines include manual interventions such as:

- manual/biased ROI selection
- arbitrary interactive parameter adjustment (e.g. manual intensity thresholds)
- non-reproducible click sequences

Typical consequences

- results cannot be reproduced and method handover to other users fails
- introduction of user / confirmation bias
- analyses are not scalable nor traceable

How to avoid it

- automation of recurring steps
- automatic randomization of ROI selection if possible to reduce user bias
- clear separation between exploratory analysis and final pipelines
- training in proper image analysis pipeline creation and the use of well documented scripts (e.g. ImageJ macros) for automation and documentation

Pitfall 6: Insufficient Documentation

Problem

Pipelines often exist only:

- in the minds of individual users
- as loose sequences of tool settings (often defined by “trial and error”)
- without version control of different pipelines

Typical consequences

- loss of knowledge when personnel change and inherited mistakes
- lack of traceability for reviewers or collaborators
- high onboarding effort for new users (by core facility or PIs)

How to avoid it

- documentation of pipeline logic (not just parameter values)
- version control and centralized storage for scripts for reproducibility
- training in writing “readable” analysis documentation and analysis scripts

Pitfall 7: Missing Institutional Integration

Problem

Image analysis is often treated as an individual skill rather than an institutional competence.

Typical consequences

- redundant analyses
- inconsistent methodologies
- overload of core facilities

How to avoid it

- structured training programs (at early career levels)
- sound understanding of analysis methods and impact on data and results
- defined minimum standards
- combination of training and centrally provided pipelines

Recommendations for Institutions

Based on the pitfalls described above, the following measures have proven effective:

1. **Foundational training for all new users**
2. **Standardized analysis workflows for common data types**
3. **Automation of recurring analysis tasks**
4. **Documented handover of analyses pipelines**
5. **Storage and publication of versioned analysis pipelines for reproducibility**
6. **Regular review and updating of existing workflows**

Conclusion

Most problems in bioimage analysis pipelines arise **not from incorrect software**, but from:

- lack of structure or guidance
- insufficient standardization
- inadequate or missing training

By combining **methodological training**, **clear workflows**, and **automation**, these issues can be avoided sustainably. Institutions benefit not only from higher data quality, but also from more efficient processes and improved reproducibility.

About BioVoxel

Since 2012, BioVoxel has been supporting research institutions with structured training in bioimage analysis and the development of customized analysis pipelines and software solutions.

Further information:

<https://www.biovoxxel.de>

